

**Designing a Cultural Probe for Language Learning:
A Qualitative Case Study**

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Designing a Cultural Probe

Kolik jazyků znáš, tolikrát jsi člověkem.

(The more languages you know, the more you are human. Or lit.

“As many languages you know, as many times you are a human being.”)

Tomáš Garrigue Masaryk, Czech

Introduction

The research that includes a qualitative interview and cultural probe kit is conducted with the aim of informing and enhancing the practice of design, or "research for art and design" (Frayling, 1993), focusing on the practical and applied aspects of language learning. The research is inspired by IDEO's design thinking process, a human-centered approach to problem-solving that involves five stages: empathize, define, ideate, prototype, and test (Design Thinking, 2019).

Qualitative interview (ethnography and interviewing)

A qualitative interview was conducted to gather primary information about participant's experiences, thoughts, and feelings regarding the process of language learning (Weiss, 1995). The interview was conducted online using the Google Meet platform. The approach posed the following limitations: the inability to correctly see non-verbal expressions of the interviewee as his facial changes and body language as the conversation progresses. To compensate for the drawback of the remote interviewing, more reflective questions were included. In other words, the respondent was directly asked about his attitude towards the questions asked during the interview (example: How do

you feel about this topic/ question? Is it comfortable for you to talk about it? What are you feeling talking about X?)

Having prepared general questions about languages and language learning, I approached the interview with an open mind and a willingness to iterate, following the natural flow of the conversation. There are two types of questions. The first consists of generalizable questions that were prepared beforehand to have an overall theme of the interview. However, as the conversation evolved, new questions were developed on its bases. They are the second type. Worth noticing the order of the questions and their structure had to be changed depending on the respondent's answers; therefore, the following lists are comprehensive and not numbered.

Questions List I: General questions prepared for the interview

We are constantly surrounded by a number of different languages. Not just because of the constant traveling around the globe but also because of our diverse student body. How do you think it affects you?

How did you come to the place regarding languages where you are now?

How have you been learning languages so far?

What attracts you on the language learning journey?

What do you not like about learning languages?

Why would you want to learn a language other than languages that you know?

How different is it to learn a language for you compared to other people?

What language have you been trying to learn, if any? What has been stopping you?

Questions List II: Questions developed on the basis of the interview

Are you learning any languages now?

Why did you quit learning Korean?

How would you define the plateau of a language "being hard"?

What are some ways of learning a new language that you know? What have you used?

Is there anything special about your way of learning a language?

Why do you think Pimsler and Language Sound are ineffective?

What is effective for language learning?

What conditions are beneficial for language learning?

What techniques do you find working for you?

What does put you off of the language learning process?

What is your reason to learn another language?

Figure 1. Jottings from the qualitative interview

Interview insights

- “There are no roads to learn a new language, only foot trails,” participant says. In other words, there is no universal approach to learning: people have different needs and circumstances; and it is OK.
- There is a “plateau” when a language becomes hard — it is the period of transition from one skill milestone to another. Usually, it is the time when people quit learning a language because it becomes 1) too repetitive, hence, too boring 2) too hard. The reasons reinforce each other since the hardness makes a learner repeat and review more, which makes the process boring.
- Participant does not trust the learning process if it is based merely on listening. His position is that if one cannot spell, read, write the language, they do not know the language.
- The ideal language learning process is the dense lessons where he can see progress after every “language learning attempt” and stable routine.
- He claims that one can say that they learn the language only after 6 months as they can maintain the conversation.
- Best learning conditions would be the presence of friends that are native speakers of the target language.
- Respondent’s motivation for learning a new language is self-development.

Interview results summary

Participant’s insights from the interview highlight some key considerations for language learning design. He recognizes that there is no universal approach to learning a new language and that individual differences and circumstances must be taken into account. He places a high value on being

able to see progress after each language learning attempt and prefers a stable routine for language learning. He also identifies the presence of native-speaker friends as an ideal learning condition and is motivated by self-development.

Based on the information from the qualitative interview with the respondent, it is possible to identify two main recurring problems related to his personal experience of learning foreign languages. Both of them are related to the presented-by-participant notion of the “plateau of hardness”, that consists of boredom and repeatedness, that in turn are the effects of a language getting harder during the transition between levels of language skills (from A to B, B to C, according to the CEFR scale, 1991). However, it is also important to meet the needs of a learner while addressing these problems. Knowing that significant user needs are an instant gratification after every learning session, which should be noticeable progress in the language, with the clear emphasis on the ability to “see the language” (know how to read and spell), the questions to guide the design thinking should be:

- ***How to overcome the negative effects of transition between language levels that make the user quit the process?***

The question, although the most relevant to the respondent and worth exploring as a direct result of the qualitative interview, would not work as the informing question of the next step of the research, the cultural probe (explored in more detail in the next section of the study). It would require the participant to transition between the language levels for a more precise result. Moreover, as of the start of the cultural probe kit, the respondent started learning the target language, which puts him in the position of a beginner, or level A1 (CEFR, 1991). While one might argue that the beginner learner can experience the same “plateau of hardness” as the learner transitioning from one level to another, the respondent made the distinction between the two phases. Thus, the decision was made to

generalize the first question and shift the attention from a stage in language learning to its effects.

Therefore, the questions for the next steps of design thinking are:

- *Is it possible to avoid negative emotions from language learning?*
- *Is the dynamic repetitiveness and boredom a sufficient cause for a learner to quit learning the language? Are there any other contributing factors?¹*

Cultural Probe: Ideation²

The qualitative interview reveals that culture and emotional state impact on language learning of the respondent; thus, the cultural probe should deepen this information by adding more contextual details from the life circumstances of the interviewee, such that the potential design solutions are appropriate. The cultural probe is needed in this research because while designing culturally sensitive and relevant interventions or programs, cognitive factors of the user have to be prioritized, hence, studied comprehensively; and the cultural probe is one of the most effective approaches in the design practice in this case (Gaver et al., 1999). Another objective of the cultural probe was to explore the role of language learning in the social life of a participant. According to the practice theory (Julier, 2007), consumption can be viewed as a social practice that involves not only individual actions but also shared understandings, rules, and norms; thus, there was an attempt to find the link between material and immaterial elements in the process of language learning.

The cultural probe's format is digital and entirely based on Notion.com, "a freemium productivity and note-taking web application" (Wikipedia Contributors, 2023), due to location differences with the respondent. When cultural probes are conducted digitally, some obstacles can

¹ #ah113-interviewsurvey: see Appendix B.

² #designthinking and #ah113-designthinking: see Appendix B.

occur (See Table 1); however, the tools and process design is directed to minimize the potential impact of these obstacles on the data collected.

Table 1. Obstacles that might occur with the cultural probe being digital and how they have been addressed

Obstacle	Description	How it was addressed
Technology barriers	Some participants may not be familiar with or comfortable using digital tools, which can affect their ability to complete the cultural probe accurately.	Made sure my respondent was comfortable with the platform with the cultural probe kit — he turned out to be an experienced user already, which gave me, as a researcher, a lot of freedom in activities creation.
Technical difficulties	There may be technical issues with the digital tools, such as glitches or crashes, which can result in incomplete or lost data.	Prior to conducting the cultural probe, thoroughly tested the digital tools and addressed any technical issues that may arise.
Privacy concerns	Participants may be concerned about their data being collected and stored digitally, especially if they are asked to provide personal information.	Uphold transparency about how participant data would be collected, stored, and used, and ensure that their privacy is protected. Used encryption to protect sensitive information.
Limited creativity	Some digital tools may not allow for as much creativity as physical tools, such as drawing or collage materials, which can limit the types of data that participants can collect.	Provided the participant with a variety of digital tools that allow for creativity and self-expression, such as digital drawing and emoji implementation.
Lack of physical artifacts	With digital cultural probes, there may be a lack of physical artifacts that can provide context and depth to the data collected	Incorporated physical artifacts into the digital cultural probe, such as asking the participant to take pictures of physical objects or locations that are meaningful to him.

Limited scope	Digital cultural probes may be limited in scope, as they are often designed to collect specific types of data or from specific populations.	Combined digital cultural probes with other research methods, such as qualitative interview as a prior step, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic.
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Ideation and prototype steps for the cultural probe kit were conducted using brainstorming (Figure 1) and empathy mapping (Figure 2) based on the results from the interview considering the constraints mentioned above of digital format and addressing the potential obstacles. The focus of activities was based on participant's prioritization and emotional responses.

Figure 1. Brainstorming for the cultural probe kit

Figure 2. Empathy mapping (language learning)

Before sending the kit to the respondent, it was essential to test it, which helped to identify several drawbacks of the current approach. Significant factors were omitted: the constraints of time and accessibility. After the mock test of the kit, the average time of compilation of a kit daily was approximated to an hour, which was not feasible for the participant as learning a new language is time-consuming. The respondent notified that he only sometimes makes language learning a daily habit, which might distort the quantitative results governed by the cultural probe. However, the time constraints of the project deadline and the respondent's schedule made the 3-day language learning cultural probe kit the most optimal trade-off.

Another disadvantage of the pilot kit was the absence of reflection before the learning sessions, which might limit the possibility of getting valuable information about participant's thought process with incentives and disincentives. Moreover, considering the main research questions of

overcoming the negative effects of the language learning process, that would limit the ability to analyze the association between quantitative variables. It was decided to divide the reflection journal into two sections: questions to answer before and after learning. The First part was focused on anticipation and expectations of the learning session that the participant had. In contrast, the second part, completed after the session, was supposed to target to what extent respondent's predictions aligned with reality and how they influenced the study process and emotional state.

Cultural Probe: Results

After the iteration and test, the final version of the kit was created (See Appendix A). It consisted of three days of repetitive, interactive, reflection-based activities to see emotional and behavioral changes as the learning progressed. To meet participant's needs regarding time constraints, the compilation of the kit takes 30-40 minutes daily; however, it does not make it less effective since the focus of the probe is not to diversify data through the range of activities but to identify patterns and trends related to the difficulties of language learning that might not be apparent from a single interaction or interview.

The first step, before any learning yet, a cultural probe was given a task to create a comprehensive to-do list for the next three days of study. This list is a representation of language priorities. As seen in Figure 3, the respondent's objective for the study was to have a basic conversation in Polish and learn the spelling of 30 words. Referring to his field of expertise and interests, we might suggest that the respondent's need and preference to measure his progress quantitatively: number of words or phrases learned, time spent on learning, and pages read in a foreign language.

Figure 3. Three-day language learning cultural probe kit — landing page

Next, daily, the respondent had to 1) create a small language to-do list for a day based on the main plan, 2) track the time of the session (when and for how long), 3) reflect on the process of learning before and after learning (See Figure 4 for an example) as well as 4) documenting the process by taking pictures of the learning surrounding. All to-do lists represented the broken-down main list, emphasizing specific language topics like basic greetings, slang, or conversation about the weather. Each session was short, taking up 20-30 minutes around the afternoon, showing that the respondent's approach to language learning as the time to fill out the break in-between work or academics, which implies that it should be fruitful to give motivation and boost of energy afterward.

Finally, at the end of the three-day cultural probe, the participant had to conclude and reflect on the progress and his emotional state of how satisfied or dissatisfied with his work he was, trying to pinpoint particular activities that caused one or another emotion (Figure 5). Interestingly, the

participant commented that “having low-key expectations” made him feel “empowered for taking larger lessons” than intended. The tools the participant used during the probe were Anki and Mango Languages and YouTube. The chosen apps have also confirmed the learning preferences of the participant, showing his inclination towards quantitative valuation like words learned (Anki), the ability to spell (Anki and Mango Languages), casual, peer-like, conversational (peer tutoring in Mango Languages and the topics of YouTube videos watched like Polish slang, etc.) However, no activities that would cause negative emotions were identified suggesting that the participant avoided them. Therefore, although in the reflection diary, the respondent mentioned that the “most challenging part would be to sit through all the repetition of the words,” which turned out to be accurate and got voiced by a participant in 3 out of 3 his reflections after studying (“doing Anki flashcards is painful when you need to concede that you have made a mistake or forgot something”), the overall attitude towards the action was positive, possible because of the instant gratitude and the measurability of progress.

Figure 4. Three-day language learning cultural probe kit — Reflection Journal

Journal-Reflection

!! Add an icon that would encapsulate your language experience today!

▼ Questions to answer BEFORE any learning yet:

- What do you expect to be the most challenging part of today's learning session(s)?
 - most challenging part would be to sit through all the repetition of the words that it seems I know already yet the long term consolidation of which haven't happened yet.
- What do you anticipate not enjoying during today's session(s)?
 - I anticipate to enjoy it in its totality, thank you very much
- What distractions or external factors do you anticipate interfering with your ability to learn effectively today?
 - Instagram, YouTube, you name it! But once I'm in the language app, I'm ready to roll, nothing can stop me.
- How will you measure your success and progress during today's session(s)?
 - I will measure in "classes" or "units" within the apps, as well new words learned
- Are there any potential challenges or obstacles that you foresee that may hinder your ability to learn today?
 - Nope

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▼ Questions to answer AFTER any learning yet:

- Did you find it difficult to start the session? If so, why?
 - A bit, I procrastinated whole day on it.
- Were there any challenges or obstacles that hindered your ability to learn today?
Procrastinatlooon
- What was the most challenging aspect of the learning session? Why?
Most challenging would be next day when I'd need to recall the words from the previous day
- Did you measure your success and progress during today's session(s)?
I completed my Anki flashcards and the unit in Mango Languages, as always
- What activities did you enjoy? Why?
I enjoyed working with both apps, since they are free and straightforward

Figure 5. Three-day language learning cultural probe kit — Conclusion

Design Audience and Solutions³

A CS student, experienced traveler and bi-lingual from childhood (Ukrainian and Russian), the cultural respondent is a good representation of international students that want to learn a new language for the purpose of self-development and enriching their social capital. They want to learn fastly and effectively, using dynamic, interactive platforms with involvement of native speakers as language peers. Teachers, student books and language routines with repetitive exercises are not appealing for this type of audience, since they mostly see a new language as a tool that they want to start using as soon as the learning process starts. They seek instant gratification and obvious measurable progress after every learning session as their motivation to continue the process. The biggest drawback in language learning for this type of audience is boredom that comes with repetition, which in turn serves as a remedy to unfamiliarity and hardness of a target language. Nevertheless, as the cultural probe showed, if the repetition is accompanied by a higher level gratification in a form of learner's progress validation, the negative emotions such as unfulfillment,

³ ah113-designforwhom: see Appendix B.

dissatisfaction and boredom can be overcome. It is important since repetition most of the time makes the progress, according to a study by Pimsleur (1967), "repetition of learning materials over a longer period of time leads to better retention and recall of the material."

Based on the clear picture of the potential users and guided by the main design thinking questions (*Is it possible to avoid negative emotions from language learning? Is the dynamic repetitiveness and boredom a sufficient cause for a learner to quit learning the language? Are there any other contributing factors?*) one of the possible design solutions can be an interactive gamified platform for language learners. Gamification has been shown to increase motivation and engagement in learning, which can lead to a sense of accomplishment and gratification. According to research by Kapp (2012), gamification can "promote a sense of accomplishment, encourage learners to achieve their goals, and make the learning experience more enjoyable."

The platform could incorporate features such as personalized learning paths, real-time feedback as a result of the involvement of native speakers as language peers, and gamified challenges that promote engagement and motivation. Additionally, the platform can show a learner's progress quantitatively as the number of words learned, grammar rules mastered, or even time spent practicing. These metrics can provide a tangible measure of progress and serve as a source of gratification for learners. Addressing the respondent's need to emphasize the visual part of the language, such as spelling and reading, the platform could also incorporate interactive activities such as word matching, sentence completion, and pronunciation practice. Moreover, the platform could offer personalized feedback on areas that need improvement and suggest targeted exercises to address those areas. By providing a comprehensive and interactive learning experience that addresses the needs and preferences of the audience, the gamified language learning platform could increase learner

engagement and ultimately lead to a greater sense of gratification and success in language acquisition, motivating the audience to continue their studies.

However, the respondent's preferences are not shared by all language learners. For example, avoidance of listening-based language approaches is rare among people that try to learn a new language. According to a study published in the Journal of International Education Research, the Pimsleur Method was one of the most effective language learning programs in a study comparing it to other popular language learning programs; while a survey of language learners conducted by FluentU found that 31% of respondents had used the Pimsleur Method in their language learning journey, indicating a significant level of popularity. Pimsleur Method is a language learning approach solely based on listening and speaking skills through structured audio lessons that gradually increase in difficulty.

For some language learners, particularly those older or more accustomed to traditional learning methods, a digital or gamified language learning platform may not be as effective as a more traditional approach. For example, a learner looking to master complex grammar rules or build a strong foundation in vocabulary may prefer a textbook-based approach that allows for more focused and structured learning.

Similarly, learners interested in immersing themselves in the culture and customs of the language they are learning may benefit more from a traditional language program incorporating in-person classes or cultural experiences. These learners may value the social interactions and human connections often inherent in traditional language learning methods and may find it more challenging to develop these connections in a digital or gamified learning environment.

Future Research

Several aspects of the research and design solutions should be addressed in the future exploration of the topic.

Firstly, during the kit completion, the respondent was learning the Polish language, which is highly similar to his mother tongue. Polish and Ukrainian share 1,167 words (37.7%) that are similar in meaning and form (Dyachenko, A. 2018). This information has to be taken into consideration as the process of learning a drastically different foreign language (compared to mother tongue) might lead to different emotional responses, which in turn should require different design approaches and strategies.

Secondly, the design solution of heavy incorporation of instant gratification through gamification of language learning leads to the question about possible cognitive effects that a student might experience in the long run. A study published in the journal *Personality and Individual Differences* found that learners who were more focused on immediate rewards and outcomes tended to have lower levels of persistence in language learning, while those who were more willing to delay gratification had higher levels of success (Zhang & Huang, 2017). Another study published in the *Journal of Educational Psychology* found that learners who were given immediate feedback on their performance tended to perform better on subsequent tasks but were also more likely to experience anxiety and stress (Butler & Winne, 1995). Overall, instant gratification as a tool for learning should be studied further and used thoughtfully with possible balance with a focus on long-term goals and a willingness to engage in challenging learning tasks.

Appendix

The link to Three-day Cultural Probe Kit on Notion.com

<https://www.notion.so/Language-Learning-Three-day-Cultural-Probe-Kit-cdf5afbae8954c5fbc0e388656afc5f2?pvs=4>

The link to Three-day Cultural Probe Kit on Notion.com (completed by the respondent)

<https://maize-noise-00d.notion.site/Language-Learning-Three-day-Cultural-Probe-Kit-bcee6f4a11fa40249a03195b6a50b06d>

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